

Mixed Realities as NIMEs

Sam Bilbow
Post-Doctoral Researcher
Experimental Music Technologies Lab
School of Media, Arts & Humanities
University of Sussex
Brighton, United Kingdom
s.bilbow@sussex.ac.uk

Yichen Wang
PhD Candidate
The Sound, Music and Creative Computing Lab
School of Computing
The Australian National University
Canberra, Australia
yichen.wang@anu.edu.au

1. WORKSHOP TITLE

Mixed Realities as NIMEs

2. WORKSHOP DESCRIPTION

The last several years have seen XR (extended / all reality) applications bloom in popularity and development within the NIME field. These have included systems, experiences, compositions, and performances on the spectrum between Augmented / Mixed Reality (AR/MR), and Virtual Reality (VR). Despite a rich history of appropriating and creatively exploiting the affordances of similar technologies, the use of specifically MR as a medium for sound-driven forms of computational art, e.g. instrument design, sound installation, audiovisual experiences, is still nascent and underdeveloped in comparison with visual forms of art [11, 17].

Inspired by recent XR workshops by colleagues, collaborators, and researchers [9, 8, 12], as well as recent advances in compositional [15, 2, 18, 19, 1] and performative ecosystems [7, 13, 3, 14, 5] this workshop aims to bring together practitioners specifically interested in augmented and mixed reality applications in music and the sonic arts. These projects have been run parallel to the current theoretical and practical trend of challenging the prevalent, ocularcentric view of MR technologies [16, 10, 4, 6], which in turn has been necessary in carving out a space for applying MR as a medium for artistic expression through NIMEs.

Thus, the purpose of the workshop is fourfold, firstly we aim to connect traditionally separated works and creative practices, under the umbrella term of 'Mixed Reality NIMEs'. Secondly, we wish to co-develop a bottom-up and cross-disciplinary perspective on MR within the NIME field. Thirdly, to seed a community built on theoretical discussions of XR concepts and the practice of MR within the NIME field. Lastly, we wish to provoke discussion around the role and availability of low-cost, open-source, and frugal approaches to adopting MR in the NIME community.

In addition to panel speakers, organisers and demo submissions, we welcome all NIME attendees who are interested in mixed reality experiences, particularly to attendees whose works align with AR/MR. This can include, but is not limited to, practitioners interested in or currently working with mixed reality in the NIME contexts of:

- Musical Composition

- Musical Notation
- Musical Performance
- Sonic Installation
- Embedded instrument systems
- Generative audio systems
- AI and ML audio systems
- Low-cost and open-source AR/MR systems

2.1 Schedule

The workshop is structured so as to generate organic thinking and discussions based on the work and presentations of the panel speakers and the submitted demonstrations, which naturally arise out of and across multiple disciplines (see Table 1). The day starts with a 40 minute lightning talk section, consisting of six sets of six minute presentations, containing up to six slides each. These will be delivered by the six panel speakers, (see more in subsection 2.2). This is followed by a short 10 minute section to address immediate questions from the workshop participants. A 10 minute break is preceded but simultaneously runs alongside, a 20 demonstration session where participants have a chance to take part / view / hear cutting edge mixed reality NIMEs. A live camera feed will be provided to virtual attendees, and pre-recorded videos will also be provided.

The second part of the workshop starts with a break-out brainstorm session, where teams of 3-4 people (including participants and panel speakers, depending on attendance) draw out common themes between the panel presentations, as well as the demonstrations. These will be fed-forward into the round-table discussion, in which the panel speakers and organisers will have a chance to follow up on questions from the lightning talks, as well as generate new theories and avenues of practice for mixed reality NIMEs. The last twenty minutes will be reserved for community building, contact exchange, and wrap-up reflections.

2.2 Panel Speakers

We have contacted and received confirmation that the following diverse and transdisciplinary set of world-leading researchers and practitioners are able to attend (in person or online) as panel speakers:

Anil Çamcı (interaction design in arts and MR)

*Assistant Professor, Performing Arts Technology,
University of Michigan*

Rob Hamilton (sonic performance in mixed reality)

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). Copyright remains with the author(s).

NIME'23, 31 May–2 June, 2023, Mexico City, Mexico.

<i>Time</i>	<i>Duration</i>	<i>Event</i>
10:00	10 mins	Organiser Introductions
10:10	40 mins	Panel Presentations
10:50	10 mins	Presentation Questions
11:00	20 mins	Participant Demos
11:20	10 mins	Break
11:30	20 mins	Brainstorm Groups
11:50	50 mins	Round-table Discussion
12:40	15 mins	Reflections and Wrap-up
12:55	5 mins	Closing Remarks
13:00	–	Workshop Ends

Table 1: A Schedule of the Workshop Events (assuming a 10am start)

*Associate Professor of Music and Media,
Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute*

Cécile Chevalier (embodiment & AR) ¹

Senior Lecturer in Media Practice, University of Sussex

Amy Brandon (AR system design and performance)

Founder, The 21st Century Guitar

Florent Berthaut (projective MR experience) ²

Assistant Professor, Computer Science, Université de Lille

Hanna Schraffenberger (holistic AR design)

Assistant Professor, Digital Security, Radboud University

3. SHORT DESCRIPTION

The increased use of mixed reality (MR) as a platform for NIME development has appeared out of different disciplines, including the arts, humanities, and computer science, but are potentially restrained by their own fields. With this workshop, we aim to facilitate and co-construct a narrative around the role of MR as NIMEs, and develop a community built on existing concepts of MR through panel talks, demos and theory-generating discussions.

4. WORKSHOP ORGANISATION

4.1 Organiser Team

Sam Bilbow

*Post-Doctoral Researcher,
Experimental Music Technologies Lab,
University of Sussex*

Sam’s research (PhD pending examination) examines the intersection between musical composition and performance, and augmented reality technologies and processes from a multisensory perspective. Sam was granted a post-doctoral fellowship at the University of Sussex in 2023, examining collaborative musical experience in low-cost and open-source AR systems. Sam has experience co-organising interdisciplinary conferences and workshops.

¹or **Chris Kiefer**, *Senior Lecturer in Music Technology, University of Sussex*

²or **Luke Dahl**, *Assistant Professor of Composition and Computer Technologies, University of Virginia*

Yichen Wang

*PhD Candidate,
The Sound, Music and Creative Computing Lab,
The Australian National University*

Yichen’s research combines human-computer interaction discipline in computer science with artistic practice in new musical interface and expression design.

4.2 Preferred Length

We plan to hold a half-day workshop in the morning, so as to allow for virtual attendance from different time zones.

4.3 Technical Requirements

- A large projector for remote panel speakers, demo and NIME general attendees
- Speakers & Microphone for in-person participants
- Several HDMI monitor so that demo submissions can be presented through laptops

4.4 Work Timeline

Table 2 shows the timeline of tasks that will take place if the current workshop paper is accepted.

<i>Date</i>	<i>Task</i>
28th Feb.	Notification from NIME
1st Mar.	Call for demos, selection and notification for successful submissions
20th Mar.	Selection of demos
27th Mar.	Notification for demo submissions
1st Apr.	Final confirmation with panels attendees about remote or in-person
1st Apr.	Complete website hosting panel information and schedule
7th Apr.	Confirmation of requirements with NIME
10th Apr.	Advertising to potential participants
28th May.	Set-up in venue

Table 2: List of tasks to complete prior to start of NIME’23 if accepted

4.5 Links to Supporting Media

Further workshop information will be hosted on the open-source XR arts community website: The XRt Space. Asynchronous communication will be available via its Discord server.

4.6 Ethical Standards

Sam’s research is funded by the Leverhulme Trust Doctoral Scholarship and Post-Doctoral Fellow Programme: *From Sensation and Perception to Awareness*. There are no potential conflicts of interest, and workshop participants are free not to take part in the demonstrations. The workshop research does not involve non-human animals.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] C. Arslan, F. Berthaut, A. Beuchey, P. Cambourian, and A. Paté. Vibrating shapes : Design and evolution of a spatial augmented reality interface for actuated instruments. In *NIME 2022*, June 2022.
- [2] F. Berthaut and L. Dahl. BOEUF: A Unified Framework for Modeling and Designing Digital Orchestras. In R. Kronland-Martinet, M. Aramaki, and S. Ystad, editors, *Music, Mind, and Embodiment*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, pages 153–166, Cham, 2016. Springer International Publishing.
- [3] F. Berthaut and L. Dahl. The Effect of Visualisation Level and Situational Visibility in Co-located Digital Musical Ensembles. In *International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, June 2022.
- [4] S. Bilbow. Developing Multisensory Augmented Reality As A Medium For Computational Artists. In *Proceedings of the Fifteenth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*, pages 1–7, Salzburg Austria, Feb. 2021. ACM.
- [5] S. Bilbow. Evaluating polaris~ - An Audiovisual Augmented Reality Experience Built on Open-Source Hardware and Software. In *NIME 2022*, The University of Auckland, New Zealand, June 2022. New Interfaces for Musical Expression PubPub.
- [6] S. Bilbow, C. Kiefer, and C. Chevalier. The Value of Sound within a Multisensory Approach to AR in the Arts. In *Proceedings of the Multisensory Augmented Reality Workshop*, page 8, Italy, 2021. Interact.
- [7] A. Brandon. Hidden Motive: On the development of interactive graphic scores for AR and VR. *The Association of Canadian Women Composers (ACWC)*, (Fall / Winter 2018):19–28, 2018.
- [8] A. Çamcı, F. Berthaut, and A. Çağan. XRMI 2021: Audio Mostly 2021 Workshop on XR Musical Instruments, 2021.
- [9] C. Chevalier and C. Kiefer. The Forum for Immersive Augmented Reality Instruments, July 2017.
- [10] C. Chevalier and C. Kiefer. What Does Augmented Reality Mean as a Medium of Expression for Computational Artists? *Leonardo*, 53(3):263–267, May 2020.
- [11] A. Dey, M. Billingham, R. W. Lindeman, and J. E. Swan. A Systematic Review of 10 Years of Augmented Reality Usability Studies: 2005 to 2014. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, 5:37, Apr. 2018.
- [12] K. Karunanayaka, A. Nijholt, T. Halloluwa, N. Ranasinghe, M. Wickramasinghe, and D. Vyas. Multisensory Augmented Reality. In C. Ardito, R. Lanzilotti, A. Malizia, H. Petrie, A. Piccinno, G. Desolda, and K. Inkpen, editors, *Human-Computer Interaction – INTERACT 2021*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, pages 558–563, Cham, 2021. Springer International Publishing.
- [13] C. Kiefer and C. Chevalier. Towards new modes of collective musical expression through audio augmented reality. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, pages 25–28, Virginia, USA, June 2018.
- [14] G. Santini. Linear: A multi-device augmented reality environment for interactive notation and music improvisation. In V. Tiffon, J. Bell, and C. de Paiva Santana, editors, *Proceedings of the International Conference on Technologies for Music Notation and Representation – TENOR’2022*, pages 37–43, Marseille, France, 2022. PRISM Laboratory.
- [15] H. Schraffenberger and E. van der Heide. Sonically Tangible Objects. In *xCoAx 2015: Proceedings of the Third Conference on Computation, Communication, Aesthetics and X.*, pages 233–248, Glasgow, Scotland, 2015.
- [16] H. Schraffenberger and E. van der Heide. Multimodal augmented reality: The norm rather than the exception. In *Proceedings of the 2016 Workshop on Multimodal Virtual and Augmented Reality - MVAR ’16*, pages 1–6, Tokyo, Japan, 2016. ACM Press.
- [17] L. Turchet, R. Hamilton, and A. Çamcı. Music in Extended Realities. *IEEE Access*, 9, 2021.
- [18] Y. Wang and C. Martin. Cubing Sound: Designing a NIME for Head-mounted Augmented Reality. *International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, June 2022.
- [19] Y. Wang and C. Martin. Designing sound synthesis interfaces for head-mounted augmented reality. In *2022 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)*, pages 351–353, 2022.